

Various perspectives of Literary criticism on the works of Literature

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Abstract- What is Literary Criticism:- Literary criticism analyzes, interprets, and evaluates works of literature. Though you most often find criticism in the form of an essay, in dept book reviews may also be considered criticism. Criticism may analyze an individual work of literature. It may also examine an author's body of work. Literary criticism is the act of Interpreting literature. Author presents us with work that can have multiple meaning, expecting us to consider thoughtfully to interpret. Writers and critics build on each others' understanding of a work of Literature in a kind of dialog. Noted authors often have a body of criticism attached to their work. Critics evaluate and debate the ideas of fellow critics. Good criticism can help us develop a better understanding of a work. It can help us develop a point of view about a work, whether as not we agree with the opinions of the critic.

Keywords: Literary criticism involves analysis, interpretation, and evaluation of literary works. It includes essays and in-depth reviews, focuses on individual texts or an author's body of work, and emphasizes multiple meanings and thoughtful interpretation. It is a dialogue between writers and critics, involving debate, discussion, and differing viewpoints. Good criticism helps develop understanding, perspective, and personal opinion about literature.

I. Introduction

Types of criticism:- Historicism considers the literary work in light of "what really happened" during the period reflected in that work It insists that to understand a piece, we need to understand the author's biography and social background, ideas circulating at the time, and the cultural milieu. Historicism also "finds significance in the ways a particular work resembles or differs from other works of its period and or genes. And therefore may involve source studies. It may also include examination of philology and linguistics. It is typically a discipline involving impressively extensor research.

New criticism examines the relationship between a text's ideas and its forms, the connection between what a text says and the way it's said "New critics/formalist" May find tension, irony, Paradox in this relation but they usually resolve it into unity and coherence of meaning New critics look for patterns of sound, imagery Narrative structure. Point of view and others techniques distensible on close reading of "the work itself" They insist that the meaning of a text should not be confused with the authors intentions nor the text affective dimensions – its efforts on the readers.

II. Archetypal criticism:-

traces cultural and psychological myths that shape the meaning of texts. Archetypes may include motifs such as the quest as the heavenly assent, symbols such as the apple as snakes or images such as crucifixion.

III. Psychoanalytic criticism:-

adopts the methods of “reading” employed by Freud and later theorists to interpret what a text really indicates. Psychoanalytic critics focus on apparent dilemmas and conflict in a work and attempt to read on authors own family life and traumas Psychological material.

IV. Feminist criticism:-

Examines gender politics in works and traces the subtle construction of Masculinity and femininity, and their relative stakes Positioning and marginalisations within works.

V. Marxist criticism:-

examines how some works attempt to share up an oppressive social orders or how they idealize social conflict out of existence, how others offers an alternative collective life or propose a utopian vision as a solution. The Marxist critic simply is a careful reader or viewer who keeps in mind issues of powers and money and any of the working following kinds of questions.

- What role does class play in the work; what is the author’s analysis of class
- Relations.
- How do characters overcome oppression?
- In what ways does the work serve as propaganda for the status quo: or
- Does it try to undermine it?
- What does the work say about oppression: or are social conflicts ignored
- Or blamed elsewhere?
- Does the work propose some form of utopian vision as a solution to the
- Problems encountered in the work?

VI. Cultural criticism:-

Cultural criticism questions traditional value hierarchies and takes a cross disciplinary approach to work traditionally marginalized by the aesthetic ideology of white European males. Instead of more attention to the Canon, cultural studies examines works for minority ethnic groups and post colonial writers and the products of folk, urban and Mass culture. Popular literature, soap opera, rock and rap music, cartoons, professional wrestling food etc. all fall within the domain of cultural criticism Historical Criticism:- Historical Critics focus on revealing the historically specific model of truth and authority reflected in a given work.

VII. Reader-Response criticism:-

Reader- Response criticism insists that all literature is a structure of experience. Not just a form or meaning and therefore focuses on finding meaning in the act of reading itself and examines the ways individual readers and communities of readers experience texts. They examine “The significance of the series of interpretations the reader goes through in the process of reading.”

VIII. Biographical criticism:-

Valuable Literature is that which tells us truths about the period which produced them we According to this approach, a vision of human nature or the world in general as filtered through an author’s individual insight and perceptions.

IX. Theoretical criticism:-

Propose a theory of literature and general principles as to how to approach it; criteria for evaluation emerge.

X. Impressionistic criticism:-

Appreciates the responses evoked by works of literature with oohs and ahhs regarding “the soul” and declarations of Masterpieces.

Mimetic criticism:- Seeks to evaluate Literature as an imitation or representation of life.
Expressive criticism:- Gushes about how well an author expressed or conveyed him or herself, his or her visions and feelings.

XI. Practical/ Applied criticism:-

Discusses particulars works and authors; the theoretical principles are implicit within the analysis or interpretation.

XII. Pragmatic criticism:-

Decides how well a work achieves its aims due to the authors strategies.

XIII. Textual criticism:-

Aims to establish an accurate uncorrupted original text identical with what the author intended. This may involve collating Manuscripts and printed versions, deciding on the validity of rediscovered version or chapters, deciphering damaged manuscripts and illegible hand writing etc.

XIV. Judicial criticism:-

Attempts to analysis and explain those effects through the basic forms of “dissection” subject style, organization techniques.

XV. Structuralism criticism:-

Structuralism is concerned not so much with what things mean, but how they mean; structuralists often would break myths into their smallest units, and realign corresponding ones opposite terms modulate unit resolved or reconciled by on intermediary third term. Structuralism was a reaction to modern alienation and despair; it sought to recover literature from the isolation in which it had been studied, since laws governing it governs all sign systems- clothing food, body language etc.

XVI. Deconstruction criticism:-

Deconstructive criticism posits an undecidability by meaning for all texts has intertwined and contradictory discourse, gap and incoherencies, since language itself is unstable and arbitrary. The critic doesn't undermine the text; the text already dismantles itself. Its rhetoric subverts or undermines its ostensible meaning.

Critical theory articulates what we bring to literature what we get out of it this is not a chaos of subjectivity. Instead, critical theory tries to examine what types of questions we should pose about literary works. What does “Common sense” say about this?” That literature is about life, or is a reflection of life.

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